

Q&As About Creative Biolabs

Creative Biolabs is specialized in providing custom biotechnology and pharmaceutical services that cover the full scope of biotechnology needs of early drug discovery and development. As a trusted provider of the most cost-effective outsourcing solutions, Creative Biolabs has been working for a large number of clients from biotechnology and pharmaceutical companies as well as government and academic research laboratories all over the world.

What is the company's mission?

Its mission is to help researchers and scientists achieve their goals in the field of antibody related studies, by providing them with reliable products, services and customized solutions. It strives to be more than just a service provider, but a research partner that customers can rely on in exploring more in antibody study.

Describe the company's most popular service offering.

Creative Biolabs has 3 main branches of services, antibody discovery, engineering and bio-manufacturing. Among them, [antibody engineering](#) services are by far the most popular offerings, such as antibody sequencing, antibody gene editing and post translational modification.

Why should customers use its services? Does it save time and/or money and/or provide access to innovation?

[Creative Biolabs](#) was founded by a group of scientists dedicated to the conquering of life-threatening diseases, therefore, it knows for sure about what the researchers and scientists expect from service suppliers like us. Since the establishment in 2005, it has been working for a large number of clients from biotechnology and pharmaceutical companies as well as government and academic research laboratories from over 26 countries, saving them plenty of time and money. Its scientists group always works closely with the clients. They are available for any consults about the project 24 hours a day, so as to push forward the processes smoothly.

What new services, tools or technologies will it offer over the next 2 years?

[Antibody humanization](#) will be its major focus in the next two years. Of course, it will also continue to expand our services in antibody discovery, engineering and bio-manufacturing.

What is the company doing to remain an industry leader?

Its marketing department and research team always follow closely with the biotech market especially antibody focused areas, by inviting client reviews, doing marketing researches, attending international conferences and so on. In this way, it can always know what the market is currently looking for. Besides, it'll have one expert team follow closely with every process of each project from our clients, so as to make everything perfect.

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